

PLANNING AND DEVELOPMENT OF INTERNATIONAL HUMAN RESOURCES AS AN ENTRY POINT FOR RAISING LOCAL ADMINISTRATIVE EFFICIENCY AND EFFECTIVENESS: ZAIN TELECOMMUNICATIONS CASE STUDY

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Abstract

This study aimed to explore the role of international human resources planning and development (training, participation in decision making, motivation, and oversight) as an entry point to raise the level of efficiency and effectiveness by: defining development and planning each one by one and linking it to the concept of human resources to identify efficiency, effectiveness. In addition to introduce suggestions and recommendations to the firms, and to future research in similar topics. A sample (80) employees of Zain Communications company was taken, working in human resources departments. (71) resolutions deemed fit for analysis recovered. The most important research findings that there is positive statistically significant influence for human resources management practices (training, participating in decision-making, motivation, and oversight)) in raising the level of efficiency and effectiveness. The study recommends that the department should rely on the empowerment of employees on their willingness to assume responsibilities, and outsourcing like consultants is another option, consultant that can lead the process.

Keywords: Human Resources, Training, Participation in Decision Making, Motivation, Oversight, Zain Communication Company.

INTRODUCTION

The general framework of the study:

Human resources are the main focus of attention in the contemporary world as the most important element and pillars of development, and the basis for moving the wheels of growth and development in the developing countries that focus on the development of ambitious programs of human development based on scientific foundations, human resources are the basic wealth of any service or productive organization, it is the main and the most elements of production.

The planning and development of human resources is one of the important means used by organizations to increase their efficiency and effectiveness, depending mainly on the success or failure of the organizations' efforts to achieve their objectives of survival, stability, expansion, growth, productivity, profitability, improved services and the

achievement of the necessary advantage in this era full of different environmental variable.

Based on the above, we will discuss in this paper the international human resources planning and development as an entry point for raising efficiency and effectiveness in organizations.

The problem of the study:

The problem of study can be expressed by the following question:

*What is the role of international human resources planning and development as an entry point for raising efficiency and effectiveness in organizations?

These sub-questions are derived from the main question of the study?

- How well does the organization understand the importance of human resources planning and development?
- How well does the organization understand the concept and importance of efficiency and effectiveness?
- How well do organizations understand the concept and importance of human resources planning and development and their role in achieving efficiency and effectiveness?

The objectives of this study aim to know the role of international human resources planning and development as an entry point to raise the level of efficiency and effectiveness by: defining development and planning each one by one and linking it to the concept of human resources to identify efficiency, effectiveness and the ability of human resources in achieving them, to learn how to invest development and human resources planning, and its role in achieving efficiency and effectiveness in the organization.

The importance of the study

the importance of the study demonstrates by targeting the subject of human resources planning and development as a means of achieving efficiency and effectiveness, providing human resources planning and development, and guiding it to what is consistent with efficiency, effectiveness and control of human resources in the organization, and employing human resources planning and development in achieving efficiency and effectiveness in the organization, by studying the following variables: training, participation in decision-making, motivation, and oversight.

The study hypotheses:

The main hypothesis: **There is no statistically significant relationship between the development and planning of human resources (Training, Participation in decision making, Motivation, and Oversight) and the upgrading of the efficiency and effectiveness of international organizations.**

The following hypotheses are derived from them:

- 1) There is no statistically significant relationship between training and efficiency and effectiveness in international organizations.
- 2) There is no statistically significant relationship between participation in decision-making and efficiency and effectiveness in international organizations.
- 3) There is no statistically significant relationship between motivation and efficiency and effectiveness in international organizations.
- 4) There is no statistically significant relationship between oversight and efficiency and effectiveness in international organizations.

Model of this study:

The Methodology of the Study

descriptive analysis being the appropriate methodology for this type of study.

Community of The Study: the study community is one of the employees of Zain Telecommunications company in Jordan and estimated number (419), being considered one of the international companies and which is full of many branches around the world.

Sample of The Study: A sample (80) employees of Zain Communications company was taken.

Data Collection Methods:

- Reference was used with the literature of study, references, published periodicals, magazines and previous studies of the subject.
- Field visits were made to the organization, and the questionnaire designed by the researchers was distributed to the sample of the study and collected and analyzed statistically to obtain the results of the study.

Tests tools for the study:

Validity and reliability tests: the stability of the tool - Kronbach Alpha. Statistical methods used: calculation averages, standard deviations, correlation measures, relationships.

Procedural definitions:

Planning: is a clever practice to interact with facts and attitudes as they actually are, and try to find solutions to come problems.

Human Resources: A series of decisions on career relationships that influence the effectiveness of the organization and staff, it designs and preparation of human resources management objectives, policies and activities in a way that achieves harmony and consistency with other management objectives in the organization.

Efficiency: To use the resources available in the highest-yielding way by satisfying the needs and desires of working individuals and raising their morale to enhance their drive to work.

Effectiveness: The organization's ability to achieve its objectives, whatever the potential used, represents the relationship between the goals achieved and the specific objectives.

Theoretical Framework:

Today, organizations are characterized by the availability and accessibility of technology, as well as the physical, administrative and financial potential of all of them, and all organizations can work to develop and increase their work. However, this is done only by obtaining a qualified human staff capable of keeping up with these developments, with high capacity for achievement, thinking and development, and all organizations are now competing for these development. The organization must therefore work to develop and develop its human resources and to increase its efficiency and effectiveness. This part will address the definition of the terms of the study and the literature that dealt with the subject in all its aspects.

Human Resources Development and Planning: Development: Its concepts have multiplied to the point where they have created a kind of confusion between them and other concepts such as development, progress and growth. **Economist Schumpeter** was the first to try to distinguish between growth and development. Growth is usually caused by population growth, wealth and savings, while development is produced by technical progress and innovation, and growth is the occurrence of quantitative changes in some economic variables. Development involves qualitative changes in these variables. This shows that growth precedes development, a phenomenon that occurs in the short term, while development is resolved only in the long term and can only be judged after a relatively long period of time (Ajami, 2010).

Thus, growth is a process of continuous automatic, steady and gradual development that occurs in a certain aspect of life, while development is a process of achieving a deliberate and lasting cumulative increase that occurs over a period of time and needs a strong impetus through the efforts of an organization that takes society out of recession and underdevelopment to progress and growth. Studies indicate that the problem of underdeveloped countries is not in need of mere growth, but in their need for development.

Planning: Organizations were not created by accident, but are the result of generational developments and human experiences throughout the ages, and planning is therefore the result of those developments. The roots of planning date back to the days of the Greeks, specifically during the era of Plato, who indirectly referred to the concept and process of planning through his virtuous republic.

Planning is a new system introduced only in the 1920s, where the two world wars drew attention to the importance of planning both to win the war and to reconstruct what was destroyed by the war. Planning is "a smart practice to interact with facts and attitudes as they actually are and try to find solutions to upcoming problems" (Al-Musawi and Jassim, 2012).

For Human Resources: There are many definitions in terms of wording but agree in substance: (Saleh, 2002) referred to a set of concepts related to human resources:

- a series of decisions on career relationships affecting the effectiveness of the organization and the effectiveness of staff.
- It is the process of attracting and developing individuals, and maintaining them in the framework of achieving the goals of the organization and achieving the goals of the workers.
- Involve human resources management in the organization's comprehensive strategic planning.
- Consider that the human component is an investment asset that must be managed and developed effectively and efficiently if the organization is to achieve "increased productivity and outperformance" in the long term.
- Programs must be designed, and policies must be tailored to employees' economic and emotional requirements.
- Create a career climate in the field of work in a way that helps employees to deliver their full potential and exploits their skills and abilities.
- Designing and preparing objectives, policies and activities of human resources management in a way that achieves harmony and harmony among them as well as harmony and consistency with the rest of the objectives and activities of other management sectors of the organization

Human Resources Planning and Development: (Saleh, 2002) indicates that the planning and development of human resources is going through several stages:

First: Study of the organization's plans and objectives: this study helps to identify the organization's human resources needs in the coming period of time.

Second: Analysis of the organization's environment: the analysis is two-way: analysis of the external environment: all relevant external factors affecting the labor market are examined, such as the composition of human resources in terms of age, gender, level of education and culture, as well as the study of government legislation affecting the labor market, general economic conditions, geographical factors, conditions of competition for

human resources, technological development, change in job occupancy (particularly the crowding of women into men in many jobs), as well as the study of social values and their relationship to employment.

Internal Environment Analysis: This is done by examining the size and type of skills, expertise and capabilities and comparing them to supply and demand in the labor market, and through this analysis we review current positions with the aim of identifying the strengths and weaknesses of jobs and employees, in addition to the process of skill auditing where a detailed analysis of employees and their level of skills is carried out to find out the gap between what exists and what should be.

Third: Predicting future human resources needs: this is done by taking advantage of information collected in the previous phase.

Fourth: Compare labor supply and demand: this is done through the organization's demand-side vacancies and labor-side labor market.

Fifth: The proposal and adoption of the plan: in the light of the comparison of supply and demand in the previous plan, and if the comparison shows a shortage of labor, the organization must fill this shortfall by attracting new employment or training existing employment, and if the comparison shows a surplus of labor, it needs appropriate solutions to lay off part of the workers, freeze the current situation or urge workers to apply for early retirement or temporary lay-offs of some workers.

Human resources development is a human resources management activity designed to develop skills, attitudes, etc., for enterprise employees that are part of the overall concept of human resources management. It places importance on training activities and covers other aspects such as career progression and turnover, and the overall objective of human resources development activities is to identify strategies for improving human resources management, with a view to obtaining a delicate balance between individual development and personnel management, within the organization, taking into account external constraints. The essence of human resources management is that all members of the organization consider "resources" available to the organization under certain circumstances. Human resource development is an investment that must be achieved economically and socially. The types of human resource development exits may be as follows:

- quality or efficiency of the working environment.
- Productivity.
- Satisfaction with work.
- The development of individuals.
- Prepare for change.

Al-Ajami, 2010, defined human resources management as the department that performs administrative functions for obtaining, developing, compensating and maintaining individuals in order to achieve the objectives of the enterprise.

Efficiency and effectiveness (Najat, 2006): The linguistic scientist Chomsky has shown that know-how is the basis of efficiency, representing an evolutionary mix of experiences, values, information and experiences that in turn form a framework for evaluating and integrating new experiences and information.

Knowledge is therefore the reference base for the formation of knowledge, and it enters as an essential element of efficiency. From a strategic point of view, competencies can be defined as "the sum of practical knowledge that ensures competitive excellence in the market. It can also be defined as "the majority in the use of available resources in a way that achieves the highest productivity by satisfying the needs and desires of working individuals and raising their morale to enhance their desire and motivation to work."

Types of competencies: Competencies are classified as:

1- Individual and collective competencies: whatever the level of individuals in the organizational structure, the positions they hold require a certain competence to perform their tasks in a way that achieves the objectives of the institution and the following is the presentation of the competencies that should be provided in individuals.

- Perseverance and the ability to work and adapt to changing and mysterious circumstances.
- The ability to learn quickly and control technological techniques.
- Recruit talent, deal positively with subordinates and the enterprise can obtain individual efficiency by adopting local standards and foundations in the recruitment process.

While collective competencies are one of the areas of growing interest of institutions, they arise through the synergy and cooperation of individual competencies, through the process of communication between them, information exchange, cooperation and conflict management.

2- Strategic competencies: The competencies and capabilities of the employees must be identified and compared with those required to achieve the strategic objectives of the organization. The strategic competencies of the organization are not only related to human resources because the efficiency of the individual is formed through the sum of individual qualities "knowledge, skill, behavior", while competencies as the ability to work in an effective manner are not related to one individual but are based on mechanisms of cooperation within the establishment of relationships of mutual influence.

In other words, strategic efficiency comes from the way in which integration between individual competencies and specific coordination mechanisms is created. Strategic competencies can be developed from three types of resources:

- physical resources (equipment, technology, buildings... etc.
- Human resources (capabilities, skills, knowledge, ... Etc.)
- organizational resources (structuring, control, ... etc.)

3- Organizational competencies: The organizational competencies of the enterprise are linked to the extent to which changes are responding at the level of its surroundings, and the transformations, complexity and instability of the competitive environment require economic institutions to have high flexibility in the management of their human resources, in order to give them the freedom to innovate and develop their individual or collective competencies, because flexible institutions are often efficient in allocating their material and human resources. (Saleh, 2002).

Effectiveness: Since effectiveness is important in the lives of organizations as a result of great development and intense competition for survival and continuity, a number of researchers and interested sought to find a theory adopted by organizations to be effective, but the subject of effectiveness is a complex subject with the complexity of the organizations themselves and this has led to many differences about the identification of their concept, and the control and measurement of their indicators, and possibly due to the difficulty of identifying phenomena surrounding the effectiveness of organizations.

Definition of effectiveness: (Smalali, 2004) defined the effectiveness as "the ability of the organization to achieve its objectives and this capacity and criteria used to measure it on the model used in the study of organizations" Bernard defined it as:"the degree to which the organization can achieve its objectives", as alvar pointed out that effectiveness means : "the ability of the organization to survive, adapt and grow regardless of the objectives it achieves", and this concept focuses on the environment as much as the organization adapts and its internal and external conditions as much as it remains an effective organization. Researchers define them as the ability to achieve goals whatever the potential used. They represent the relationship between the goals achieved and the specific objectives. From the above, it is clear that it is difficult to agree on a specific definition of effectiveness, and not all dimensions of effectiveness are as important in measuring the effectiveness of the Organization.

The difference between efficiency and effectiveness: (Ajami, 2010) Showing the difference between efficiency and effectiveness is by highlighting the meaning that both take, effectiveness is usually seen from the point of view of the results reached by the workers and therefore the work is described as effective if it achieves the ruler's goals and is less effective if it cannot achieve them, and from this concept we can differentiate between effectiveness and efficiency.

We say that: Effectiveness is the exploitation of available resources in achieving the specific objectives, i.e. they are about achieving efficient results, the means or the way in which results have been achieved or achieved. The concept of efficiency is inherent to the concept of effectiveness, but it should not be used interchangeably, the organization may be effective but not efficient, i.e. it achieves its objectives but at a loss, and the incompetence of the organization negatively affects its effectiveness, the higher the costs of achieving a particular goal, the less likely the organization will be able to survive. Both efficiency and effectiveness must be taken into account within the measures of success of an organization, the effectiveness is to get the job done or the right thing, but efficiency is to get the job done properly. and the organization may be efficient but not efficient.

Previous studies:

- **(Hiregoudar and Patil, 2020)**: entitled: The Impact of Training and Development on Organizational Overall Performance in IT Industry. The study has interviewed workers to examine the factors that impacts on the performance of the employees. Upon interviewing the IT Industry employees, they said that the IT industry employees are happy with their respective training and development programmes. It has also been concluded in this study that employee satisfaction, work security, and financial benefits are the main factors in employee performance growth. Management with a focus on improving employees will strengthen the interest and commitment of employees to the job.

- **(Abu juladaydah, 2018)** entitled "The Impact of Human Resource Management Strategies on the Performance of Employees in the Libyan Telecommunication Companies" The aim of this study is to know the impact of human resource management strategies on the performance of employees in Libyan telecommunications companies. The study population included all employees of top and middle management of the Libyan telecommunications companies (Almadar Aljadid and Libyana Company), the study shows its high interest in the strategy of Training and Development, in line with the continuous technological development in the field of telecommunications. The study also showed the high interest of the employees in the Libyan telecom companies in the requirements of commitment to work, and keen to apply the correct values and keep away from the negative phenomena resulting from delays in work and evasion of performance, and keenness on the outputs of the work accomplished (quality and quantity) to perform the work as required.

- **(Jassim and Al-Mousawi, 2012)** entitled "The reality of human development and its vision for the future in Iraq". The study aimed to reach advanced forms of social well-being of Iraqi society and create an enabling environment in which people's capacities can be strengthened, expand their options as well as understand the Iraqi reality and seek logical solutions to eradicate poverty and seek to create a vision through which to understand the role of human development in economic and social development as well as address structural imbalances in the reality of development requirements. The study relied on the descriptive analytical curriculum, and the study community was from the education sector in Iraq and the study resulted in a weakness in the capacity and tariff capacity of schools and school buildings that limits the chances of boys and girls enrolling in or continuing education and the study recommended the need to advocate a new vision of education and training systems.

- **(Ali, 2013)**: entitled "Human resources development and its social reflection". The aim of the study was to clarify the concepts of development and sustainable development and its great interest in various sciences, including social sciences that seek to improve the individual's living by developing skills and planning for optimal investment in order to promote and present them to society and follow the best scientific means in this, the study has reached some results and recommendations, the most important of which is to regulate the movement of the workforce with the aim of solving the problem of imbalance

in the labor market and linking social planning policy with policies of social planning Workforce planning.

- **Sheikh's 2012** study entitled "The impact of the development and training of human resources working in the tourism sector on tourism development in Syria" its aimed at solving the reality of the tourism sector in Sura, and to know the impact of development and training on this sector and its positives. The researcher adopted the descriptive analysis curriculum, and the study was aimed as a society with the tourism sector and vocational schools that teach and train in the profession of tourism. The study came up with several results, the most important of which is that the education and tourism training programs do not meet the needs of development in Sura at the moment, and suffer from weaknesses, the most important of which is the incompetence of the training staff, the numbers of They are emerging from the tourism education institutions in decline and fluctuation from year to year, and most workers in the tourism sector are among the other qualified scientifically and specializedly. The study recommended giving first-hand education and interpretation in tourism development plans, as a cultural and cultural necessity and as a way of tourism.

- **(Al-Hayali and Al-Obaidi, 2012)** entitled "Reflecting regulatory values in the development of the human resource is an analytical study of the opinions of a sample of the administrative leadership at Mosul University". The study aimed to show the outstanding between organizational values the development of the human resource, and to clarify the concepts of values and human resources and their impact on the organization. The study used the descriptive analytical approach, and the study community was made up of administrative leaders at Mosul University. The study produced several findings and recommendations, the most important of which is that organizational values are of great importance, that the human resource is the most important in the performance of the organization, that both values and human resources are greatly affected by each other, and recommended that they take care of human resources and values, which reflects on performance.

THE METHOD AND PROCEDURES

The method and procedures describe the study community, its sample, the tool used, the procedures for its construction and development, the steps needed to achieve its validity and stability, and the statistical methods used to gain knowledge of the results of the study.

The community of the study and its sample: The study community will be made up of Zain employees and the estimated number of people (419).

Sample of the study: The sample of the study was made up of 80 Zain workers, 71 of whom were responded to and considered valid for analysis as follows, depending on their demographic characteristics as follows:

Table (1): Study sample according to the study variables

Percentage %	amount	Level	Variable
49.3%	35	Male	Sex
50.7%	36	Female	
26.8%	19	20-25 year	Age
59.2%	42	26-30 year	
9.9%	7	31-35 year	
4.2%	3	36-40 year	
.0%	0	More than 40 year	
12.7%	9	High school or less	Scientific qualification
70.4%	50	Deploma/bachelor	
16.9%	12	High study	
32.4%	23	Less than 5 years	Years of work
52.1%	37	5-10 years	
9.9%	7	11-15 years	
4.2%	3	16-20 years	
1.4%	1	More than 20 years	
18.3%	13	High level management	Administrative level
81.7%	58	Middle level management	
.0%	0	Lower level management	

Study tool: The researchers used a questionnaire of 34 paragraphs, belonging to the areas of study and the distribution of paragraphs as follow:

Part 1: Demographic variables (sex, age, scientific qualification, years of work, administrative level)

Part II: Questionnaire questions by hypotheses: as follows

- 1) Training - paragraphs (1-7)
- 2) Participation in decision-making - paragraphs (8-14)
- 3) motivation - paragraphs (15-21)
- 4) oversight - paragraphs (22-27)
- 5) Dependent variable: Efficiency and effectiveness of 28-34

The validity of the tool: To verify the authenticity of the tool, the questionnaire was presented to a group of specialists, and after reviewing suggestions and observations, where the researchers adopted the paragraphs that were approved, after some paragraphs that were not fully representative of the axis in which they were placed were deleted, and all paragraphs agreed to be invalid or modified in accordance with the nature of the study were deleted. **Stability of the tool (resolution):** In order to verify the stability of the study tool, the Kronbach Alpha equation was used to calculate the stability factor for all areas of the study tool, which numbered (5) areas, reaching the value of stability calculated on the basis of the total score (0.90). Presenting and discussing the results includes a presentation of the statistical results reached after analyzing the data of the study tool, and will reveal the indications of differences in the variables of the study, and to know the nature of the relationship between variables, by answering the questions of the study.

Findings on the main study question: What is the role, development and planning of human resources as an entry point for raising efficiency and effectiveness in the organization? To answer this question, the researcher extracted mathematical averages and standard deviations of the study tool areas, as shown in the following table:

Table (2): Calculation averages and standard deviations of study tool areas ranked downwards by calculation averages

Standard Deviation	Mathematical Averages	Variable(Study Tool)	Rank
.60299	4.2012	Participation in decision-making	1.
.69507	4.0728	Oversight	2.
.53176	3.9054	Efficiency and effectiveness	3.
.48682	3.8632	Motivation	4.
.59383	3.7606	Training	5.
.45856	3.9606	Average tools	

The previous table shows that the calculation averages tools of the study came high, where the field of participation in decision-making came first with an average account of 4.2 followed, the oversight field with an average account of 4.07, while in the last place came the field of training with an average account of 3.7.

Mathematical averages and standard deviations of study area paragraphs were also extracted, as follows:

The training:

Table (3): Mathematical averages and standard deviations for training

Level	Standard Deviations	Mathematical Averages	Paragraphs	No.
High	1.00422	4.1408	All employees are given the same job attention.	1.
High	1.09746	3.9014	The environment surrounding the work is comfortable and stimulating	2.
High	1.07299	3.8592	The workers in the training programs are committed to applying them at work	3.
High	.90472	3.8451	Staff receive appropriate training programs	4.
High	.98500	3.7324	The ministry's training and development department aims to increase efficiency	5.
High	1.11907	3.4648	Managers take into account the psychological state of the staff when designing the exercises	6.
High	1.15098	3.3803	Managers take into account the right times in the training process	7.
High	.59383	3.7606	Training	

The previous table shows that the calculation averages for paragraphs in this area came high, with the paragraph (all employees are given the same job attention) ranked first with the highest arithmetic average (4.1408), a standard deviation (1.00422), followed by a paragraph (the environment surrounding work comfortable and stimulating) in second place, with an average calculation (3.9014) and a standard deviation (1.0976). In the last place, the paragraph that reads (managers take into account the right times in the

training process) came with an average account (3.3803) and a standard deviation (1.15098).

Participation in decision making:

Table (4): Mathematical averages and standard deviations for Participation in decision making

Level	Standard Deviations	Mathematical Averages	Paragraphs	No.
high	1.01557	4.3521	Managers consult those who are below their job grade before making a decision	1.
High	.87464	4.3239	Management has clear foundations in the decision-making process	2.
high	1.04448	4.2817	The Department trains decision-making workers	3.
high	.90583	4.2535	The decision-making process is rational and conscious	4.
high	.84038	4.2535	The decision-making process is conducted on scientific grounds	5.
high	.89037	4.0845	All employees seek to rationalize decision-making processes	6.
High	1.08622	3.8592	The ministry allows employees to participate in decision-making	7.
high	.60299	4.2012	participate in decision-making	

The previous table shows that the calculation averages of paragraphs in this area came at a high level, with the paragraph that reads (managers consult those with the lowest job score before making a decision) ranked first with the highest account average of (4.3521), and Standard deviation (1.01557), followed by a paragraph (management follows clear foundations in the decision-making process) in second place, with an average calculation (4.3239) and a standard deviation (.87464). In the last place, the paragraph (the ministry allows employees to participate in decision-making) came with an average calculation (3.8592) and a standard deviation (1.08622).

Motivation:

Table (5) calculation averages and standard deviations for the motivation

level	standard deviations	Mathematical averages	Paragraphs	No.
high	.95597	4.1690	Administrative empowerment gives employees an opportunity to demonstrate their abilities	1.
High	.91884	4.1127	Employees do their jobs well when motivated	2.
High	1.00702	3.9859	When motivated, employees feel high self-confidence	3.
high	1.06565	3.9155	Motivating employees pushes them towards creativity and the development of working methods	4.
high	1.15534	3.7465	Management encourages employees to take responsibility by motivating them	5.
High	1.08992	3.5915	Motivation helps employees achieve promotion to higher office	6.
high	1.18151	3.5211	Management depends on the empowerment of employees on their willingness to assume responsibilities	7.
high	.48682	3.8632	Motivation	

The previous table shows that the calculation averages for paragraphs in this area came high, with the paragraph (administrative empowerment giving staff the opportunity to prove their abilities) ranked first with the highest arithmetic average (4.1690), a standard deviation (.95,597), followed by a paragraph (staff perform well when motivated) in second place, with an average account (4.1127) and a standard deviation (.91884). In the last place was the paragraph that reads (the administration adopts the empowerment of employees on the extent to which they are willing to assume responsibilities) with an average account (3.5211) and a standard deviation (1.18151).

Oversight:

Table (6): Calculation averages and standard deviations for the oversight

level	standard deviations	Mathematical averages	Paragraphs	No.
High	.91180	4.3521	The regulatory process produces positive and stimulating results	1.
High	.96310	4.2394	Oversight officers seek correction, not punishment	2.
High	1.02288	4.1972	The regulatory process is well and meaningful.	3.
High	1.07897	3.9155	There are controls at all levels of management	4.
High	1.08437	3.9014	The control system follows modern means of control	5.
High	1.14625	3.8310	Controls are done at a good level	6.
High	.69507	4.0728	Oversight	

The previous table shows that the calculation averages of paragraphs in this area came at a high level, with the paragraph that reads (the regulatory process produces positive and stimulating results) ranked first with the highest arithmetic average (4.3521), a standard deviation (.91,180), followed by a paragraph (oversight officers seek correction rather than punishment) in second place, with an average calculation (4.2394) and a standard deviation (.9610). In the last place was the paragraph that reads (controls are done at a good level) with an average calculation (3.8310) and a standard deviation (1.14625).

Efficiency and Effectiveness

Table (7): Calculation averages and standard deviations for efficiency and effectiveness

level	standard deviation	Mathematical averages	Paragraphs	No.
High	.91511	4.1831	I stick to time and I'm not late for work.	1.
High	.86701	4.1831	I do my job and do it without mistakes.	2.
high	1.0630	4.1127	Do the duties i'm required to do the best I can.	3.
high	1.0046	4.0704	I do the best I can with the least time and effort.	4.
high	1.12248	3.6479	I can work under pressure.	5.
high	1.0094	3.5775	I do my work and my duties without being asked.	6.
high	1.155	3.5634	I feel distracted by conflicting administrative decisions.	7.
high	.53176	3.9054	efficiency and effectiveness	

The previous table shows that the calculation averages for paragraphs in this area came at a high level, with the paragraph that reads (I commit to time and do not delay working) ranked first with the highest average calculation (4.1831), a standard deviation (.91511), followed by a paragraph (I master my work and accomplish it without mistakes) in second place, with an average account (4.1831) and a standard deviation (.86701). In the last place was the paragraph that reads (I feel distracted by conflicting administrative decisions) with an average account (3.5634) and a standard deviation (1.15551).

Testing the hypotheses of the study: The researchers conducted a monogamous test with the hypotheses, as shown in the following:

Test of the first hypothesis: There is no statistically significant relationship between training, and efficiency and effectiveness in international organizations.

Table (8): Monogamous test with hypotheses

Result	Significant	T value	Standard deviation	Mathematical averages	Domain
Accept	.000	11.360	.59383	3.7606	Training

The previous table shows that there is a statistical indication of the responses of the study sample members to the field of training, where the value of the indication was less than 0.05. It is statistically significant, which means accepting the hypothesis of the study with a statistically significant effect on efficiency and effectiveness of the independent variable.

Test of the second hypothesis: There is no statistically significant relationship between participation in decision-making, and efficiency and effectiveness in international organizations.

Table (9): Monogamous test with hypotheses

Result	Significant	T value	Standard deviation	Mathematical averages	Domain
Accept	.000	5.197	.60299	4.2012	Participation in decision making

The previous table shows that there is a statistical indication of the responses of the study sample members to the field of participation in decision-making, where the value of the indication was less than 0.05. It is statistically significant, which means accepting the hypothesis of the study with a statistically significant effect on efficiency and effectiveness of the independent variable.

Test of the third hypothesis: There is no statistically significant relationship between motivation, and efficiency and effectiveness in international organizations.

Table (10): Monogamous test with hypotheses

Result	Significant	T value	Standard deviation	Mathematical averages	domain
Accept	.000	2.803	.48682	3.8632	Motivation

The previous table shows that there is a statistical indication of the responses of the study sample members to the field of stimulation, where the value of the indication was less than 0.05. It is statistically significant, which means accepting the hypothesis of the study

with a statistically significant effect on efficiency and effectiveness of the independent variable.

Test of the fourth hypothesis: There is no statistically significant relationship between oversight, and efficiency and effectiveness in international organizations.

Table (11): Monogamous test with hypotheses

Result	significant	T value	Standard deviation	Mathematical averages	domain
Accept	.000	-1.277	.69507	4.0728	Oversight

The previous table shows that there is a statistical indication of the responses of the study sample members to the field of control, where the value of the indication was less than 0.05. It is statistically significant, which means accepting the hypothesis of the study with a statistically significant effect on efficiency and effectiveness of the independent variable.

The researchers then analyzed the variance of the study areas, to test the theories of the study, as shown in the following table:

Table (12): Simple regression analysis of the impact of independent variables on efficiency and effectiveness

Model Summary						
Model	R	R square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.924a	.854	.845	.20931		
a. Predictors: (Constant)						
ANOVA						
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	16.902	4	4.226	96.453	.000a
	Residual	2.891	66	.044		
	Total	19.794	70			
a. predictors: (Constant)						
b. Dependent Variable						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(constant) 1	.012	.238	.681	.049	.961	
Training	.610	.054	.325	11.366	.000	
Participation in decision making	.287	.055	.153	5.197	.000	
Motivation	.167	.060	-.080	2.803	.007	
Oversight	-.061	.048	.681	-1.277	.206	
a. independent variable						

The previous table shows that there is a significant correlation between the independent variable and the dependent variable, where the results showed that the value of the correlation between the independent and the dependent variable was 0.92, a positive correlation of statistical significance, as the results showed that the interpreted variance values were 0.85, i.e. 85% of the independent variable affected the dependent variable, which confirmed a value of 96.45 and a statistical allowance of less than 0.05. This means accepting the main hypothesis of the study, which provides for an impact on

efficiency and effectiveness of training, motivation, oversight, participation in decision-making.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1) Managers should take into account the right times in the training process.
- 2) The company should allow employees to participate in decision-making
- 3) The department should rely on the empowerment of employees on their willingness to assume responsibilities.
- 4) To conduct controls at a good level and take care of them.
- 5) Non-dispersal of workers through conflicting administrative decisions

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